

**VOCATIONAL INTEREST OF STUDENTS IN RELATION TO SCHOOL
ENVIRONMENT AND PERSONAL VALUES**

Hoor Jahan Hasan

Associate Professor

Anjuman-I-Islam's Akbar Peerbhoy College of Education, Vashi

Rationale of the Study

One of the most important decisions high school students make is career choice. Choice in the discipline of study defines further education and consequently what young people will do in the rest of their lives. It determines their earning capacity and often their social and economic class as well. While many other countries allow students to defer hard choices to later in their lives – mostly until the final year of college and sometimes even later – the choice made by high school students in India is more rigid than it is elsewhere.

There are good structural reasons for the rigidity. Offering students flexibility further on requires greater flexibility in the higher education system. College would have to find a way to increase the number of admitted students in one discipline over another based on the delayed choice. This kind of flexibility is expensive and in societies where capital is short, it is hard to make the necessary investment. This means that the choice students make in their study in high school has enormous and snowballing impact. Since students cannot easily change their area of study in the future, they have to make good choice early on. The importance of career counseling has only increased in recent years as the Indian economy has grown and new opportunities have emerged. These opportunities arose not only in technology fields, where learning investment may be high but also in low-investment learning areas such as in the retail and real estate industries. For students coming from lower-income Households, these industries are indeed great opportunities for advancement, but students have to learn to make necessary choices.

Yet it is hard to expect that the teenagers are sufficiently mature or have developed a sufficient complete world view to make wise decisions about what they want to do for the rest of their lives. The challenge, therefore, lies in families and schools helping young people make these choices in the most thoughtful manner possible. Formal career counseling plays an important role in determining the choices. However, what principles should guide career counselors or even parents as they dispense advice? This paper attempts to understand the origins of vocational interest among students.

Specifically, it compares vocational interest in relation to personal values and school environment. The results of this study should enable better dispensation of career advice.

Statement of the Problem

The problem of the study has been entitled and stated as under: “**VOCATIONAL INTEREST OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT AND PERSONAL VALUES.**”

Objectives

The main objectives of the study are as follow:

- (a) To study the vocational interests of girls and boys.
- (b) To compare the school environment of single sex and co- educational school.
- (c) To compare the personal values of girls and boys belonging to single sex and co- Educational schools.
- (d) To study the vocational interests of students with regard to their school environment.
- (e) To study the vocational interests of students with regard to their personal values.

Research Methodology

In the present investigation ex- post fact research method has been adopted. All the recognized Private, English Medium High Schools of Lucknow city, constitute the population of the study. The sampling was done in two stages (i) Selection of the schools were randomly selected and 120 students 30 were from single sex boy's schools (30 boys, 30 girls). Data Collection was done seeking prior permission from the principal of the selected schools. The tools used in the study were:

- a. S.P. Kulshrestha : Vocational Interest Record (VIR)
- b. Karuna Shanker Misra, School Environment Inventory (SEI)
- c. G.P. Sherry, R.P. Verma, Personal Values Questionnaire (PVQ)

The tools were administered in the free periods. Analyses of the data and interpretation of results were done section wise. Non- parametric statistics were used as the data was on nominal and ordinal scale.

For finding the significance of difference between vocational interests of girls and boys belonging to single sex and co- educational schools, the data was organized and categorized at nominal scale, frequency counts for the respective categories was calculated and X² test (2 X 2 four fold table) was applied.

Similarly, significance of difference between school environment of co-educational and single sex schools as well as significance of the difference between personal values of co- educational and single sex schools were found by using X² test (2 X 2 four fold table).

Relationship between vocational interest and school environment as well as vocational interest and student's personal values was found using tetra choric coefficient of correlation. The significance of the result was observed at 0.05 levels as well as 0.01 levels.

Results and Conclusions

- Girls of co- educational schools differ significantly to the girls of single sex schools on executive area of vocational interest.
- Boys of co- educational and single sex schools differ significantly on scientific area of vocational interest. This shows that boys belonging to co- educational schools exhibit scientific temperament.
- There is significant difference between the girls belonging to single sex and co- educational schools on creative stimulation, cognitive encouragement and permissiveness dimension of school environment.
- There is significant difference between the boys belonging to single sex and co- educational schools on creative stimulation, cognitive encouragement, acceptance rejection and control dimension of school environment. This depicts that the school environment as perceived by the boys of co- educational schools is creative, encouraging controlling as well as rejecting.
- The girls and boys belonging to single sex schools differ significantly on dimension of school environment such as creative stimulation, acceptance, rejection and control.
- The girls belonging to single sex girl's schools differ significantly from the girls of co- educational schools on dimension of personal values like religious, economic, hedonistic and family prestige. This reflects religious tendency of girls of co- educational schools in comparison to girls of single sex girls school. These girls also value family prestige higher.
- The boys belonging to single sex boy's schools differ significantly from the boys of co- educational schools on economic value. This indicates that the boys of single sex school are guided by considerations of money and material gains in the choice of their jobs as compared to their counterparts in co- educational schools.
- There exists significant difference between the personal values of girls and boys belonging to co – educational schools on family prestige value dimension.

- Creative stimulation dimension in school environment bears a positive relationship with scientific and agricultural scale of vocational interest.
- Cognitive encouragement dimension in school environment bears a positive relationship with scientific and agricultural dimension of vocational interest.
- Cognitive encouragement dimension of school environment bears negative correlation with social area vocational interest.
- Acceptance dimension in school environment bears a positive relationship with agricultural area of vocational interest. Acceptance means teachers unconditional love and recognition for his / her students encourages students to opt for professions in agricultural sphere.
- Acceptance dimension in school environment possesses negative correlation with literary and social area of vocational interest. Acceptance in a negative way reflects teacher's attitude and desire not to reform, modify changes or improve.
- Permissiveness dimension in school environment exhibits positive correlation with literary, executive, artistic and household area of vocational interest.
- Rejection dimension in school environment has a positive correlation with household area of vocational interest. By rejecting student's uniqueness, teachers build student interest in the household professions.
- Rejection dimension in school environment exhibits negative correlation with scientific and agricultural area of vocational interest.
- Control dimension of school environment bears a positive correlation with artistic and social area of vocational interest.
- Social as personal value bears a positive correlation with social and household domain of vocational interest.
- Democratic dimension of personal values has a positive correlation with executive scale of vocational interest. Democratic outlook encourages executive professions.
- Democratic values do not correlate positively with artistic choice professions.
- Aesthetic as personal value bears a negative correlation with literary, agricultural and household dimension of vocational interest.
- Aesthetic as personal value bears a negative correlation with persuasive dimension of vocational interest.
- Economic as personal value bears a positive correlation with literary scale of vocational interest. Students having materialistic bent of mind opt more for job in the literary sector.
- Economic as personal value bears a negatively correlated with constructive and persuasive dimension of vocational interest.
- Knowledge as personal value bears a positive correlation with constructive and household area of vocational interest.
- Power as personal value is positively correlated with persuasive area of vocational interest. Students having power values opt for jobs of persuasive bent as both demand a command of ruling over others mindsets.
- Power as personal value is negatively correlated with agricultural area of vocational interest.
- Hedonistic as personal value is negatively correlated with literary, persuasive and social dimension vocational interest
- Family prestige as personal value is positively correlated with persuasive and social dimension of vocational interest.

- Family prestige as personal value is negatively correlated with scientific and executive dimension of vocational interest.
- Health as personal value bears a positive correlation with executive, constructive, agricultural, persuasive and household dimension of vocational interest.

Educational Implications

The major educational implications of the present research finding are:

1. To promote literary vocations among students, there needs to be an element of non- acceptance of student by the teachers.
2. To enhance and hone literary skills among students, a permissive school environment has an important role as it allows student to express freely and fearlessly, with conviction and authority: a requisite for literary expressions.
3. To provide students with scientific bent of mind, the school environment needs to promote and stimulate student's creativity. Teachers should provide activities like brainstorming (creative problem – solving) and use divergent questioning skills to promote creativity amongst students, which will in turn promote scientific choice of vocations.
4. To provide students with the correct aptitude for sciences, the school environment must provide correct cognitive encouragement to the students.
5. To provide students with an interest for scientific professions, rejection at school level must be avoided at all costs.
6. To develop interest in executive professions, The school environment needs to be permissive type.
7. To have artistic aptitude and attitude among students, the needed school environment must be permissive type.
8. A controlled school environment is also required for interest in artistic professions.
9. Agricultural professions are encouraged when the school environment stimulates creativity and encourages cognition.
10. To increase interest in social jobs, a controlled school environment is none conducive than an environment which fosters acceptance of student's uniqueness.
11. To Enhance interest of students in household jobs, the school environment must not directly eject students, rather proper guidance & counseling must be given to those needing it.
12. To encourage students to take up executive jobs: Democratic attitude in them must be fostered. Formation of democratic values helps in creating a desire for executive jobs.
13. To enhance interest level in the constructive jobs, knowledge must be encouraged, increased and value by students for them to opt for constructive jobs.
14. Students having an interest in household jobs hold social values dear. To encourage such jobs of the household domain, imbibing values like charity, kindness, love and sympathy is a must.
15. Aesthetic values of beauty, system and order must be developed in students for them to choose social jobs in their vocational career.
16. To improve vocational interest in the literary sphere, desire for money and material gains is a needed attribute or value to developed among students. But an increase of economic value diminishes the desire constructive jobs.
17. For increase in the vocational interest is the agricultural fields, values such as system, order, neatness must be clubbed with values of self- preservation of health.
18. Students valuing family prestige opt more for jobs in the social field. To inculcate in students' desire for social jobs, they must the inculcate social values.
19. To develop interest in aesthetic jobs, value of inculcate power value increases desire for aesthetic jobs.

- Family prestige as personal value is positively correlated with persuasive and social dimension of vocational interest.
- Family prestige as personal value is negatively correlated with scientific and executive dimension of vocational interest.
- Health as personal value bears a positive correlation with executive, constructive, agricultural, persuasive and household dimension of vocational interest.

Educational Implications

The major educational implication of the present research finding are:

1. To promote literary vocations among students, there needs to be an element of non-acceptance of students by the teachers.
2. To enhance and hone literary skills among students, a permissive school environment has an important role as it allows student to express freely and fearlessly, with conviction and authority: a requisite for literary expressions.
3. To provide student with scientific bent of mind, the school environment needs to promote and stimulate student's creativity. Teachers should provide activities like brainstorming (creative problem – solving) and use divergent questioning skills to promote creativity amongst students, which will in turn promote scientific choice of vocations.
4. To provide student with the correct aptitude for sciences, the school environment must provide correct cognitive encouragement to the students.
5. To provide students with an interest for scientific professions, rejection at school level must be avoided at all costs.
6. To develop interest in executive professions, the school environment needs to be permissive nature.
7. To have artistic and attitude among students, the needed school environment must be permissive type.
8. A controlled school environment is also required for interest in artistic professions.
9. Agricultural professions are encouraged when the school environment stimulates creativity and encourages cognition.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Alan, Mecvoy & Robert, Welker (2000). AntiSocial Behavior, Academic Failure and School Climate. A Critical Review. *Journal of Emotional and Behavioral Disorders*, Val. 8 (3), p. 130.
- Anastasi, A. & Urbina, S. (2005). *Psychological Testing* (5th Indian print). Singapore. Pearson Education.
- Baba, S. S. S. Cited in somnath saraf (1999). *Education in Human Values*. New Delhi, Vikas Publishing House Private Limited, p-83.
- Baker, David P. (Nov., 1995) *The Effects of Sex – Grouped Schooling on Achievement : The role of National Consent*. *Comparative Education Review*, Vol. 39(4), The University of Chicago Press. Pp. 468-482.
- Bedi H.S. (1982). *Aspirations of Adolescents as Related to Social Economic Status, Intelligence and Sex*. Ph. D. Thesis, Department of Education, Punjab University. Best, J.W. & Khan, J.V. (2005). *Research in Education*. New Delhi, Prentice Hall of India. Borget and gilray (1994) *Vocational Interest of Professional and Non Professional College Student*. *Journal, of psychological Research*, 2001. Vol. 45(1), pp. 9-14.
- Bracher, W.E. (1982). *The Influence of the Family on Career Selection: A Family Systems Perspective*. *Personnel and Guidance Journal*, October, pp.87-91.

- Broday, S. F. (1990a). The Relationship between Response Style on the Strong- Campbell Interest Inventory and Occupational scales (for women). *Psychological Reports*. Vol. 66, pp. 94.
- Broday, S. F. (1990b). The Relationship between Response Style on the Strong- Campbell Interest Inventory and Occupational scales (for men). *Psychological Reports*. Vol. 66, pp. 374.
- Campbell, D.P. (1996). Stability of Interests with in an Occupation over Thirty Years. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 50, pp. 51-56.
- Chandan, S. S. (1978). *Advanced Educational Psychology* (6th Revised Edition). Delhi, Vikas Publishing House Private Limited.
- Collins, H (1995). *Concise Dictionary*.
- Cook, E. P. (1983). Sex Differences in the Career Choice of Students. *Journal of College Students Personnel*. Vol. 22(3), pp.256-261.
- Crites, J. D. (1961). A Model for the Measurement of Vocational Maturity. *Journal of Counselling Psychology*, pp.255-259. Das, M. (Apr. 19-25,2004). *Value Education University News*, 42(16), p.12
- Dewal, O. S. (1966). Dyan amics of Vocational Development. *Journal of Vocational and Educational Guidance*, Vol. 12(3), pp.205-206.
- Diamond, E. E. (Ed) (1975). *Issues of Sex Bias and Sex Fairness in Career Interest Inventories*. Washington D.C.: National Institute of Education.